

FIBONACCI SQUARE SUM SLITHER LABELING OF SPECIAL GRAPHS**R. SREENIVASAN**Assistant Professor, Post Graduate and Research Department of Mathematics,
Agurchand Manmull Jain College, Meenambakkam, Chennai, India

ABSTRACT: The Fibonacci numbers is a unique sequence of numbers in mathematics that has special applications. These numbers are obtained by the sum of preceding two numbers of the sequence and the numbers begin with 0 and 1. The idea of Fibonacci labeling denotes to the assignment of Fibonacci numbers to the vertices or edges or both. In this paper, the applicability of Fibonacci labeling to nigh complete bipartite graph and the Mongolian Tent graph are examined.

KEYWORDS: Fibonacci labeling, Square Sum Labeling, Slither labeling, nigh complete bipartite graph, Mongolian Tent graph.

INTRODUCTION: The specialty of the Fibonacci numbers lies in its applications that extends from the field of trading, computer algorithms to software design. Extending from these applications, the numbers also play a vital role in the recognition of development patterns in flora etc. With so much in its repertoire, the Fibonacci numbers had kindled the thoughts of the investigators around the in using these concepts to different graphs.

SIGNIFICANT DEFINITIONS:

FIBONACCI NUMBERS: The Fibonacci numbers refers to the sequence of numbers that begin with 0 and 1. The ensuing numbers in the sequence are acquired by the sum of former two numbers in the sequence.

SQUARE SUM LABELING: Square sum labeling in graphs, considered in this paper is taken from the definition given by Mitesh J. Patel and G.V. Ghodasara [2] which is as follows; "A (p, q) graph G is said to admit square sum labeling if there is a bijective map given by $f_1:V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1,2,..,p-1\}$ such that the induced function $f_1*:E(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ given by $f_1*(uv) = (f_1(u))^2 + (f_1(v))^2$, where the edge $uv \in E(G)$ is an injective map".

SLITHER LABELING: The slither labeling in graph refers to the assignment of numbers to the vertices or edges or both in the slither formation.

NIGH COMPLETE BIPARTITE GRAPH: R.C. Bunge, S.I. El-Zanati, W.O'Hanlon and C. Vanden Eynden [1] are the first researchers to define the notion of an almost bipartite graph. They also went to prove that the admittance of γ -labeling to the almost bipartite graph admits This provided the much needed zeal in defining the nigh complete bipartite graph. Also, the definition of γ -labeling has provoked the thought to define vertex antimagic edge slither labeling. The definition for the nigh complete bipartite graph or nigh graph is given as follows; let $G(V, E)$ be a graph with the vertex set $V(G)$ being sub-divided into two non-empty subsets V_1 and V_2 with the set V_1 having m vertices and V_2 having n vertices. Then the graph given by $K_{m,n} + e_1 + e_2$ is said to be a nigh graph if the removal of the edges e_1 and e_2 renders the graph complete bipartite. The number of vertices in the graph is $m + n$ and the number of edges in the graph is $mn+2$. R. Sreenivasan and M.S. Paulraj [4] proved that the nigh graph admits vertex antimagic edge labeling. R. Sreenivasan [6] proved that the nigh complete bipartite graph admits vertex antimagic edge slither labeling.

Fig 1. Nigh Complete Bipartite Graph $K_{4,4} + e_1 + e_2$

MONGOLIAN TENT GRAPH: The Mongolian Tent Graph M_n defined by Sharmila Mary Arul, K. Subashini [3], is obtained by joining a vertex on top of $P_n \times P_n$ grid with the top row vertices of the grid. The number of vertices in M_n is $n^2 + 1$ and the number of edges is $2n^2 - n$.

Fig 2. Mongolian Tent Graph M_6 .

METHODOLOGY: The vertices of the graphs are subject to slither labeling using the Fibonacci numbers in such a way that the labels of the vertices are all unique. The label of an edge is the sum of squares of labels of the vertices that are incident with it. If the labels of the edges are all unique, then the graphs are said to admit Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling.

MAIN RESULTS:

THEOREM 1: The nigh complete bipartite graph admits Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling.

Proof: Consider a nigh complete bipartite graph given by $K_{m,n} + e_1 + e_2$ ($m, n \geq 2$) where the removal of the edges e_1 and e_2 renders the graph complete bipartite.

CASE – 1: Let $m \neq n$. Let $m = 2$ and $n = 3$ be arbitrary numbers. Then the Fibonacci slither labeling of $K_{2,3} + e_1 + e_2$ is given by

Fig 3. Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling in $K_{2,3} + e_1 + e_2$

In the above graph, the labels of the vertices are done in slither formation using the Fibonacci numbers making sure that the vertex labels are all unique. The label of an edge is the sum of squares of labels of the edges that are incident with it and they are all unique as well. Hence the graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling. Since the values $m = 2$ and $n = 3$ are arbitrary, it follows that the graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling for all $m, n \geq 2$.

CASE – 2: Let $m = n$. Let $m = 3$ and $n = 3$ be arbitrary numbers. Then the Fibonacci slither labeling of $K_{3,3} + e_1 + e_2$ is given by

Fig 4. Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling in $K_{3,3} + e_1 + e_2$

In the above graph, the labels of the vertices are done in slither formation using the Fibonacci numbers making sure that the vertex labels are all unique. The label of an edge is the sum of squares of labels of the edges that are incident with it and they are all unique as well. Hence the graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling. Since the values $m = n = 3$ are arbitrary, it follows that the graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling for all $m, n \geq 2$. From the cases discussed above, it is clear that the nigh complete bipartite graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling for all $m, n \geq 2$.

THEOREM 2: The Mongolian Tent Graph admits Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling.

Proof: Consider the Mongolian Tent graph M_n formed from a grid on n vertices.

Let $n = 3$ be an arbitrary value. The Fibonacci slither labeling of M_3 is given by

Fig 5. Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling in M_3 .

In the above graph, the labels of the vertices are done in slither formation using the Fibonacci numbers making sure that the vertex labels are all unique. The label of an edge is the sum of squares of labels of the edges that are incident with it and they are all unique as well. Hence the graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling. Since the value $n = 3$ are arbitrary, it follows that the graph admits Fibonacci square sum slither labeling for all $n \geq 2$.

CONCLUSION: In this paper, the nigh complete bipartite graph and the Mongolian Tent graph have been proved to accept the Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling. Similarly, different graphs can be taken and the acceptance of Fibonacci Square Sum Slither Labeling can be verified.

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